

PEARLS

Mycotoxins: An ongoing challenge to food safety and security

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Introduction

Mycotoxins have influenced human and animal health for centuries, often with serious and sometimes deadly consequences. The earliest known cases are outbreaks of ergotism in medieval Europe, caused by alkaloids from *Claviceps purpurea* growing on rye. These epidemics, called “St Anthony’s fire”, produced convulsions, gangrene and death. Ergot-infected grain has also been suggested as a possible factor behind the symptoms recorded during the Salem witch trials in 1692 [1]. During the Second World War, people in Russia consumed overwintered grain infected by trichothecene-producing *Fusarium* species. This led to the alimentary toxic aleukia epidemic, one of the best-documented examples of human mycotoxicosis [1]. Such outbreaks demonstrate the longstanding impact of mycotoxins on societies.

The modern era of mycotoxin research began with the “Turkey X disease” outbreak in the United Kingdom in 1960, when contaminated peanut meal caused the deaths of more than 100,000 turkeys. The toxic agents were identified as aflatoxins produced by *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*, leading to the introduction of the term “mycotoxin” in 1962 [1,2]. Around the same period, sporidesmin A, produced by *Pseudopithomyces toxicarius* (then *Sporidesmium bakeri*), was identified as the causal agent of facial eczema in livestock in New Zealand [3,4]. The first human fatality from the consumption of aflatoxin-contaminated food was documented in Uganda in 1967 as fatal hepatitis [5]. These events initiated systematic research on fungal toxins in agriculture, food safety, and animal health.

Mycotoxin contamination remains a global concern in food and feed systems. Recent outbreaks of aflatoxicosis in dairy herds in Pakistan and fatal maize-related poisoning in Tanzania show that exposure persists in both animals and humans [6,7]. To date, more than 400 mycotoxins have been identified; however, only a few are regulated globally. The major agriculturally significant mycotoxin groups include aflatoxins, trichothecenes, zearalenones, ochratoxins, ergot alkaloids, fumonisins and patulin, produced mainly by *Aspergillus*, *Claviceps*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* species [2]. It is estimated that 60–80% of consumed food contains detectable mycotoxins, and about half of these samples include multiple toxins, forming the so-called “mycotoxin cocktail” [8].

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